

METHODS OF EXPLAINING THE MEANING OF WORDS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the scientific and theoretical basis of using dictionaries in primary education.

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One of the main tasks of primary classes is to develop students' speech. Speech development is carried out in three directions: working on words, working on word combinations and sentences, and working on connected speech in methodical literature. recorded.

Work on the word is carried out in the following directions: 1. Teaching the correct literary orthographic pronunciation and reading of words 2. Explanation of word meanings 3. Introducing new words to students' speech, i.e. enriching their vocabulary 4. Teaching to choose the words from the dictionary in the right place. 5. Teaching how to use words methodically 6. To teach to spell words that are part of the minimum vocabulary This chapter talks about ways to explain the meaning of new words that are unknown to students in the elementary school mother tongue textbook. This is the 2nd and 3rd listed above It also includes the 4th and 5th directions in connection with this.

The text often tells the dictionary meaning of unfamiliar or unfamiliar words to students. In such cases, they learn the meaning of such a word independently, without special explanation from the teacher. Their meaning will be explained by the teacher. In the methodology, several methods have been developed to explain the meaning of unknown words to children. These methods differ depending on the nature and meaning of the word. For example, words that have the meaning of something the best of all is to give a visual explanation to the students. In this, the thing named by the word itself or a picture is shown. About the importance of the picture in explaining the meaning of unknown words, K. D. Ushinsky wrote: : "The nature of a child requires demonstration. Teach a child some 5 unknown words, he will suffer for a long time and in vain over them. But if you connect 20 such words with actions, the child will learn them on the fly." When it is not possible to visually explain the meaning of the

word, the teacher should use one of the "semantic interpretations" and explain the meaning of the incomprehensible word in short explanatory ways. The following methods of semantic annotation can be used in the primary class: 1. The meaning of an incomprehensible word is revealed to the students by giving it several synonyms, for example: light, light, lamp, tabarruk-aziz, dignified, blessed, etc. This method is used When using the word, the teacher should consider that the synonym interpretation of the word can achieve its goal only when the students understand the meaning of each explanatory synonym. It is important to choose commonly used words. For example, the meaning of the word space should be explained not by the word space, but by the word sky. 2. The meaning of an unclear word can be explained by listing the objects (things, signs, actions) referred to by that word. For example, metal is gold, silver, iron, lead. ..., insects are butterflies, beetles, wasps, ants...

Answering in the best way to the psychological characteristics of the students in learning the meaning of the word, the listed explanations are sufficient for the correct understanding of the meaning of the word, even if this explanation does not cover all the objects that the word refers to. forms the basis. 3. The meaning of an unknown word can be explained to the students in a visual way. In such an explanation, all the necessary information about the meaning of the word is given. hanging pile: cotton threshing, wheat threshing, tradition-ancestral habit, responsibility-feeling responsible for doing something, miracle-mysterious, unexplained event, something. 4. The meaning of an unclear word can be revealed by means of a logical definition, that is, by referring to the gender relationship. after saying a word with a broader meaning indicating its belonging, the word being explained must give a type of thing, a phrase showing a different sign, or a separate word. For example, an insect, a mosquito-like insect that sucks the blood of cattle, dew-water, water that falls on plants in the evening and remains in drops in the morning, a child is a child, a human child, children are bees. , a honey bee. The use of the above-mentioned methods of explaining the meaning of words by the teacher in lexical training not only ensures that students understand and master the vocabulary they need, but also helps children connect with one or another word. It helps to expand and deepen the perception of related concepts.

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